

**ON THE ISSUE OF CHOOSING A TEXTBOOK FOR TRAINING A
SPECIALIST IN THE FIELD OF FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED
LINGUISTICS**

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the issues of bachelor's language training in the field of Fundamental and Applied Linguistics. Special attention is paid to the criteria for selecting a textbook taking into account the modern educational standard, the specifics of this area and the key competencies of a graduate of a higher school. The advantages of the innovative course "English Result" are revealed and the relevance of its use for the intensification of all levels of the educational process is confirmed.

Keywords: educational and methodological complex, functional and applied linguistics, competence, reading, speaking, listening, writing.

The Bachelor's degree program in Fundamental and Applied Linguistics is aimed at training a unique specialist whose professional activity is connected, on the one hand, with scientific research in the field of theoretical linguistics, on the other – with its various applications, i.e. It allows combining traditional areas (teaching native and foreign languages, compiling dictionaries of various types) and areas that have been developing especially rapidly in the last two decades (automatic processing and transmission of textual information, creation and development of intelligent systems, linguistic technologies in the socio-political sphere).

Focusing on the core competencies that should be formed in a student of this field of study, special attention is paid to the study of foreign languages. Mark Hancock and

Annie McDonald "English Result" can be recommended as the main textbook for the course "Foreign Language" for students of the direction "Fundamental and Applied Linguistics" (www.elt.oup.com).

"English Result" is an innovative multi-level English language course. This course has a clearly defined practical focus, providing language material and developing the speech skills necessary to solve communication problems. The course is aimed at increasing the motivation of students due to the interesting content, carefully dosed language material and the possibility of its immediate application.

Special emphasis is placed on visual design: illustrations are used to focus attention on the topic under study, create context for the use of language material, semanticize lexical units and grammatical structures, provide ideas for students' independent statements, as well as to get acquainted with the cultural realities of different countries.

The course is characterized by a positive approach to learning and self-assessment of achievements using the "I can..." scale based on the results of each lesson. An integrated approach to the expansion of language knowledge and the development of speech skills. It is the key, which is due to the practical goals of a particular lesson. When learning to speak, oral interaction and oral self-expression are separated as separate speech skills. Along with the development of language competence, increased attention is paid to the formation of socio-cultural and pragmatic competencies, which will allow students to use the language more successfully for practical purposes.

UMK "English Result" has the following package: the actual textbook Student's Book with DVD Pack, workbook Workbook (with/ without key) and MultiROM, - audio-video applications Class Audio CDs/ DVD Pack, Teacher's Book for teachers, additional tests Extra Tests, a selection of additional material Teacher's Resource Pack with DVD, digital resources for interactive learning English Result iTools.

The textbook includes 12 thematic sections (each contains the material of 5 lessons with a clearly formulated practical task "How to ...", and a lesson for repeating and consolidating the material of the section), tasks for pair work, a grammar guide

with additional exercises, a list of irregular verbs, a table of phonetic symbols and examples of basic intonation drawings, texts of audio recordings. Pages filled with visual material allow you to maintain motivation at a high level. The two-page format of the lesson makes it easy to use the course.

The main task of the workbook is to ensure the consolidation of language and speech material through a series of training exercises aimed at practicing lexical, grammatical and phonetic material, as well as tasks for the development of reading, speaking, listening and writing skills. The structure of each workbook lesson coincides with the corresponding textbook lessons. The workbook also contains tasks for repeating the material and self-control (Self Check).

The textbook and workbook are equipped with a DVD with audio and video materials for classroom and independent work. Audio recordings contain texts for listening, exercises for the development of pronunciation skills, speech patterns for building dialogical statements, songs. DVD files containing documentary sketches and interviews of an authentic nature enliven the lesson. All videos are accompanied by subtitles, which helps to connect the visual image of the word and its sound. In addition, for the rational organization of the video lesson and effective work with DVD files, a set of tasks (DVD worksheets) aimed at the formation of communicative and socio-cultural competencies has been developed.

MultiROM, which is included in the UMK kit, contains both interactive tasks and exercises, as well as an active vocabulary for each lesson and other materials designed for self-study; in addition, MultiROM provides students with free access to interactive training tests.

The book for teachers helps to organize work clearly and purposefully, without overloading students with unnecessary information. It includes:

- description of the course features, its goals and objectives; characteristics of each of the course components;
- recommendations for evaluating the success of language acquisition and practical mastery of speech skills (opportunities for testing and self-assessment);

- after-school recommendations, including cultural and linguistic explanations, mandatory and additional exercises;
- tips on preparing for a specific lesson and the expected practical result.

The structure of the book for teachers differs in that it includes all the pages of the textbook, as well as audio scripts, keys to tasks in the book for students and tests for each section. The book for the teacher is accompanied by an educational and methodical DVD, which demonstrates the use of materials and methods of the course in practice, accompanied by an author's commentary.

The teacher is offered a full set of didactic material for working in the classroom, including a variety of tasks (from crosswords to role-playing games), accompanied by explanations and recommendations, as well as test tasks for the current control and assessment of students' skills.

Thus, the English Result course is aimed at developing four language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. At the same time, much attention is paid to the use of audio, video and interactive resources, which, along with a variety of methodological techniques, contributes to the formation of skills necessary for foreign language communication. This complex, characterized by the logical presentation of the material and a gradual increase in the level of complexity, is focused on the systematization of knowledge and generalization of linguistic, speech, communicative, socio-cultural experience of students. The complex is attractive both for students, giving the opportunity to study a living modern language, and for the teacher, being a multicomponent textbook that expands the teacher's capabilities in the field of formation and improvement of foreign language communicative competence, which is a priority when training a specialist in the field of applied linguistics.

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